

Radiochromatographic Separation of Scandium(III) with Inorganic Ion Exchanger Zirconium Phosphosilicate

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A method has been developed for the adsorption of Sc^{III} employing inorganic ion exchanger zirconium phosphosilicate by batch method. Effects of various parameters have been evaluated on the percentage adsorption of Sc^{III}. Separation of Sc^{III} from various other elements is standardized.

Inorganic ion exchangers are in general superior to organic exchangers in their resistance to ionizing radiations and elevated temperatures¹. Zirconium phosphosilicate (ZPS) has been used for the isolation of plutonium from rare earths in nitric acid medium² and for the separation of Zr, Ru, Np and Bk³. The present work deals with the development of a batch method for the radiochemical separation of Sc^{III} from other elements employing ZPS ion-exchanger. ⁴⁶Sc was used as a tracer in this work.

Results and Discussion

The effect of the concentration of the exchanger (100–800 mg) on the adsorption of Sc^{III} was studied at a pH 3.5 with an equilibration time of 4 min. Adsorption of Sc^{III} increased linearly upto 400 mg of ion exchanger and thereafter it remained constant, indicating the capacity 2.5 mg/g of the exchanger. Hence, in all further studies 400 mg of ZPS was used. The % adsorption at different pH (Table 1)

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH AND TIME OF EQUILIBRATION ON THE ADSORPTION OF Sc^{III} ON ZIRCONIUM PHOSPHOSILICATE*

pH	Time of equilibration min	% Adsorption
2.0	4.0	81.5
2.5	4.0	87.9
3.0	4.0	93.3
3.5	1.0	72.1
3.5	2.0	87.1
3.5	3.0	93.2
3.5	4.0	94.2
3.5	5.0	95.3
3.5	6.0	95.5
3.5	7.0	94.6
4.0	4.0	92.5
4.5	4.0	89.9
5.0	4.0	84.2
5.5	4.0	80.4

* Reproducibility : 94.2% ± 1.9.

revealed that it attained maximum average value of 94.2% at a pH of 3.5. Effect of time of equilibration revealed that when the time was varied from 1.0 to 7.0 min the maximum adsorption was obtained at 4.0 min. Effect of metal ion concentration on the % adsorption of Sc^{III} was studied

by increasing its concentration from 0.25 to 10.0 mg and was found to be almost constant upto 1 mg of Sc^{III}, after which it decreased.

Examining the effect of different salts on the % adsorption of Sc^{III} revealed that 100 mg each of bromate, dichromate, borate, sulphite, chloride, chromate, nitrate, cyanide, nitrite, thiourea, sulphide, chlorate, thiocyanate, thiosulphate, acetate, bromide, iodide and sulphate, 50 mg each of arsenate and tartrate, 25 mg each of fluoride did not interfere in its adsorption. However, 10 mg each of oxalate, citrate and EDTA strongly interfered. Interference of these anions could be removed by decomposing them with concentrated HNO₃ and HCl prior to the adsorption.

The adsorption of other cations in presence of Sc^{III} was studied with and without addition of the carrier. The % adsorption of other elements was greater without carrier than with carrier. The adsorption of the elements with carrier revealed that Sb^V, Mo^{VI}, Sb^{III}, Re^{VII}, Hg^{II}, As^{III}, Sn^{II}, Na^I, Ru^{III}, Ca^I, Ir^{IV}, S^{VI} and Au^{III} were adsorbed between 1.0 to 10.0%. Fe^{II}, Cr^{III}, Cu^{II}, K^I, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Se^{IV}, Sr^{II} and Sn^{IV} were adsorbed to the extent of 10–50%. Tl^I, Ba^{II}, Rb^I, In^{III}, Cs^I, Fe^{III}, Pd^{II}, Ce^{III}, Ce^{IV} and Eu^{III} were adsorbed to > 50%. The interference of Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II} and Cd^{II} was suppressed to <5% by washing the exchanger with 100 mg of cyanide. Co^{II} ions were adsorbed to <1.3% by washing the exchanger with 50 mg of thiocyanate. Au^{III} ions were adsorbed to <5% by washing the exchanger with 100 mg of thiourea. Cu^{II} ions were adsorbed to <2% by washing the exchanger with 100 mg of thiosulphate. The adsorption of Ba^{II} ions decreased to about 3.5% by washing the ion exchanger with 10 ml of 0.1 N HCl and that of K^I ions to 7% by washing the ion exchanger with 10 ml of hot water. Se^{IV} ions were adsorbed to <3.8% by washing the exchanger with 25 mg of fluoride. The adsorption of Rb^I and In^{III} decreased to <7% by washing the exchanger with 100 mg of chromate. Adsorption of Cs^I ions was suppressed to <8% by washing ZPS with 100 mg of acetate. The adsorption of Sr^{II} decreased to <1% by precipitating it as sulphate prior to adsorption. The adsorption of Fe^{II} decreased to <10% by increasing the carrier to 2 mg.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. ^{46}Sc (83.9 days) and radioisotopes used were supplied by B.R.I.T., Trombay. The stock solution of Sc^{III} was prepared by dissolving ScCl_3 in double-distilled water containing concentrated HCl. Solutions of anions and cations were prepared by dissolving appropriate salts in distilled water, but 5 ml of concentrated HCl was added to the solutions of cations wherever required. The strength of these solution was determined by the standard method⁴.

ZPS was prepared by following the reported method⁵. A clear solution of water-glass ($\text{Na}_2 \times \text{SiO}_2$) was prepared by dissolving the silicate (14 g) in distilled water (100 ml). Concentrated HCl (12 ml) was then added slowly to it with constant stirring, followed by a solution of $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4.5 g in 100 ml of 1 M HCl) and stirred continuously. On addition of concentrated ammonia (35 ml), a white gel-like precipitate was obtained which was washed to nearly neutral washings. The gel was subsequently phosphatized by mixing it with mixture of 1 N H_3PO_4 (40 ml) and 1 M HNO_3 (40 ml) with stirring. The precipitate so obtained was left overnight, washed as mentioned before and dried at 200° for 6 h. The ion exchanger was then powdered.

γ -emitters were counted on a single-channel pulse-height analyser in conjunction with a 3.5 cm \times 3.5 cm NaI(Tl) flat-type crystal detector. β -emitters were counted on a thin end-window type G.M. counter in conjunction with a decade scaler, high voltage and a timer.

Batch equilibration method : A solution (10 ml) containing ^{46}Sc tracer and Sc^{III} carrier (1 mg) (pH adjusted to

3.5 with help of dilute HCl or NH_3) was added to ZPS (400 mg). The mixture was equilibrated for 4 min and then ZPS was separated from the filtrate. The activity on the exchanger was measured and the % adsorption calculated.

Separation of other metal ions from Sc^{III} : Separation of other cations from Sc^{III} on ZPS was standardized under the experimental conditions. Other cation (1.0 mg) along with its tracer was mixed with Sc^{III} (1.0 mg). The total volume of the mixture was made upto 10 ml with distilled water, its pH adjusted to 3.5 and added to ZPS (400 mg). The mixture was equilibrated for 4 min and the ion exchanger separated. The % adsorption of other metal-ions on the exchanger was calculated.

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